

Synthesis of Halotropones through Dihalocarbene Adducts

M. K. Saxena* and M. M. Bokadia

Addition of dihalocarbene to cycloalkenes and subsequent treatment of these products seems to be an elegant method for expanding ring systems^{1,2}. Parham et. al.², have reported the syntheses of 7-chloro-2,3-benzotropone (II) and 2-chloro 4,5-benzotropone (IV) in 11.5 and 13% yields respectively, by prolonged reaction of a mixture of ethyl trichloroacetate, sodium methoxide and the corresponding methoxynaphthalene at 0–5°.

We have reinvestigated the reactions of dichlorocarbene with 1- and 2-methoxynaphthalene separately and have obtained improved yields of II (20%) and IV (18%) respectively. However, in these experiments dichlorocarbene was generated by the action of chloroform on potassium *t*-butoxide in olefin free anhydrous petroleum ether at –10°. We have further studied the reaction of dibromocarbene with 1-methoxynaphthalene (I) and have isolated 7-bromo, 2,3-benzotropone (V) in 15% yield. It was characterized by its elemental analysis, oxime formation and by IR and UV spectra. The reaction goes via the dibromoadduct which could not be isolated under experimental conditions. This reaction scheme has already been established for chlorotropones by earlier workers². In like manner the reaction of dibromocarbene with 2-methoxynaphthalene (III) afforded 2-bromo 4,5-benzotropone (VI) in 11% yield.

Procedure^{2,3}: To a well cooled (–10°) stirring slurry of potassium *t*-butoxide and methoxynaphthalene in olefin free anhydrous petroleum ether (40–60°) was added haloform (diluted with 50 ml. solvent) over a period of 6 hr. The reaction mixture was left for 12 hr. at 0°, stirred again at 40° for 6 hr. and then poured into an equal volume of water. Organic layer was separated, dried (MgSO₄) and solvent recovered. Residue in each case was processed to afford the products.

* Present address: Postdoctoral fellow, Chemistry Department, I.I.T., Kanpur.

1. R. W. Murray, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 7, 27.
2. W. E. Parham, D. A. Bolon and E. E. Schweizer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 603.
3. All melting points are uncorrected.

7-Bromo 2,3-benzotropone (V): The reactants were 1-methoxynaphthalene (18.6 g., 0.12 mole), bromoform (30.30 g., 0.12 mole) and potassium *t*-butoxide from 6 g. potassium. The reaction medium was petroleum ether. From the reaction mixture 1-methoxynaphthalene was recovered by distillation under reduced pressure (129°/2.5 mm., 14 g., 80%). The residue in benzene was chromatographed on alumina (grade I) to yield golden yellow needles of 7-bromo 2,3-benzotropone (m.p. 109–110°, 4 g., 15%). Anal. Found C, 56.1; H, 2.8; Br, 34.22; C₁₁H₇BrO requires C, 56.17; H, 2.98; Br, 34.04%. IR (in chloroform) has absorption bands at 1635 (m), 1610 (m), 1695, (s), 1550 (s) cm⁻¹. UV (95% ethanol) λ_{max} mμ (log ε): 231 (4.50), 263 (4.02), 312 (3.90) and 325 (3.90). Oxime m.p. 205–206°.

2-Bromo 4,5-benzotropone (VI): The reactants were 2-methoxynaphthalene (18.6 g., 0.12 mole), bromoform (30.3 g., 0.12 mole) and potassium *t*-butoxide (from 8 g. potassium, 0.2 mole). Dry olefin free benzene was used as the reaction medium. Reaction mixture was processed in an exactly analogous way as described in the preceding experiment. There was obtained recovered 2-methoxynaphthalene (15 g., 85%) and golden needles of 2-bromo 4,5-benzotropone (m.p. 135°, 2.9 g., 11%) Anal. found C, 56.0; H, 2.8; Br, 33.56; C₁₁H₇BrO requires: C, 56.17; H, 2.98; Br, 34.04%. IR (in chloroform) has absorption bands at 1635 (s), 1610 (m), 1560 (w), 1520 (s) cm⁻¹. UV (95% ethanol) λ_{max} mμ (log ε); 238 (4.43), 275 (4.47), 340 (3.57). Oxime: light yellow crystals m.p. 196–198°.

School of Studies in Chemistry,
Vikram University,
Ujjain (M.P.).

Received December 22, 1967.
Revised MSS received July 17, 1969.